

UPCYCLED CARDBOARD BY-PRODUCTS AS FUNCTIONAL ADDITIVES IN THERMOPLASTIC STARCH-BASED BIOPLASTICS

Idalina Gonçalves, G. J. Campos, E. M. T. Gonçalves, M. Pinho, A. M. Ferreira, F.H. B. Sosa, P. Ferreira

Aveiro Institute of Materials, Department of Materials and Ceramic Engineering, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17295091
idalina@ua.pt

Abstract: *The growing demand for sustainable materials has driven research into circular strategies that valorize packaging waste. In this context, cardboard production trims, an abundant by-product of packaging manufacturing, were explored as a source of cellulose-rich nanostructures to be used as additives in thermoplastic starch (TPS)-based bioplastics. Within the scope of the BIOCOATING project, various chemical pre-treatments were evaluated to disintegrate and upcycle these cardboard residues. NaOH/urea aqueous systems and ionic liquids were applied under controlled temperature and mixing conditions to dissolve the fiber matrix and generate gel-like suspensions rich in cellulose. The resulting gels were purified, dried, and incorporated into TPS formulations developed using starch recovered from potato washing slurries. The incorporation of upcycled cardboard fractions into the TPS matrix aims to enhance film-forming ability, moisture barrier performance, and mechanical resistance, while preserving biodegradability. Preliminary results indicate that ionic liquids show a promising balance between processing efficiency and functional enhancement. This approach demonstrates a double valorization strategy, integrating cellulosic packaging waste and food processing residues into a single, biodegradable material platform for packaging applications. Upcycled cardboard-derived structures thus offer a renewable alternative to synthetic fillers and support the design of packaging materials aligned with circular economy principles.*

Acknowledgements: *This work was developed within the scope of the project CICECO-Aveiro Institute of Materials, UIDB/50011/2020 (DOI 10.54499/UIDB/50011/2020), UIDP/50011/2020 (DOI 10.54499/UIDP/50011/2020) & LA/P/0006/2020 (DOI 10.54499/LA/P/0006/2020), financed by national funds through the FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC). G.J. Campos and E.M.T. Gonçalves acknowledge the BIOCOATING project (COMPETE2030-FEDER-00590400), funded by Compete 2030, Portugal 2030, and the European Union, for the research grants. The authors also thank Isolago Europe (project leader), as well as A Saloinha and FEB Cafés, for kindly providing the agri-food by-products used in this study. I. Gonçalves acknowledges funding from FCT through the Individual Call to Scientific Employment Stimulus (<https://doi.org/10.54499/CEECIND/00430/2017/CP1459/CT0032>).*